

Correlation of Clinical, Electrocardiographic, Echocardiographic and Coronary Angiographic Profile with Outcome in Acute Inferior Wall ST Segment Elevation Myocardial Infarction: A Hospital Based Prospective Observational Study

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Abstract:

Background: Acute myocardial infarction is the most common type of coronary artery disease with variable prognosis. This study sought to determine the clinical, electrocardiographic, echocardiographic, and coronary angiographic profile in patients with inferior wall ST-elevation myocardial infarction to establish the correlation of these parameters with the observed outcomes.

Material and Methods: This observational, prospective study was conducted in 102 patients admitted with inferior wall ST-elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) at Silchar Medical College, Silchar within 12 hours of onset of symptom. The data for all the patients were collected and eligible patients were assessed for electrocardiography, echocardiography, coronary angiography and clinical profile to correlate them with in-hospital and one-month follow-up outcomes.

Results: The mean age of the study population was found to be 57.98 ± 9.02 years and majority were male (80.4%). The outcomes noted in patients during hospitalization were requirement of temporary pacemaker implantation (18.63%), cardiogenic shock (12.75%), hemodynamically significant ventricular tachycardia/ventricular fibrillation (9.8%), heart failure (5.88%) while the outcomes observed after follow-up were post MI angina in 15.22% of patients, heart-failure readmission (5.43%) and few patients developed reinfarction and other mortality (2.17%). In the study population, lower rate of mortality was observed in patients with single vessel disease (SVD) than multi vessel disease (MVD)($p=0.013$); similarly, lower rate of post MI angina was observed in patients with SVD than MVD ($p=0.02$).

Conclusion: To take rational therapeutic decisions in the management of inferior wall STEMI, it is paramount to identify the risks and outcomes using indicators such as clinical profile, electrocardiography, echocardiography, and coronary angiography parameters.

Keywords: Acute coronary syndrome; Coronary angiography; Electrocardiography; Echocardiography; ST elevation myocardial infarction.

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Introduction

Acute myocardial infarction (AMI) is the most serious manifestation of coronary artery disease which is categorized into ST elevation and non-ST elevation myocardial infarction having a tremendous global impact on morbidity and mortality in cardiac patients [1,2]. The AMI develops as a result of erosion or rupture of an atherosclerotic plaque causing a thrombotic occlusion in coronary artery leading to ischemia [3]. Over a decade, considerable improvement in prognosis has been observed as a result of various implicating trends like risk-stratification, use of invasive strategy, care delivery systems implementation which prioritizes immediate revascularization using techniques like percuta-

neous coronary intervention and coronary artery bypass grafting along with advancements made in the pharmacological approach encompassing drugs like fibrinolytic agents, antiplatelet agents and anticoagulants which are used as preventive therapy.[1] Of all types of AMI, inferior wall ST-elevation myocardial infarction accounts for about 40-50% of total cases [4,5]. From anatomical point of view, it is caused by occlusion either in right coronary artery (RCA) or left circumflex artery (LCX) [6,7]. Sometimes patients with inferior wall STEMI do not have favorable clinical outcomes and it is noticed that nearly 50% develop complications like hypotension, bradycardia, heart block, ventricular

tachycardia or right ventricular infarction which substantially alters the relatively favorable prognosis of inferior wall STEMI [8-11]. Therefore optimal risk-stratification based on clinical and biochemical profile, electrocardiography, echocardiography, coronary angiography is paramount to improve the outcome. Several studies are available which explain the short-term outcomes in patients with inferior wall STEMI using various techniques like electrocardiography, echocardiography, clinical or angiography parameters. However, the lower mortality rate in comparison to anterior wall MI is overlooked, consequently the late complications of inferior wall STEMI are generally missed. Furthermore, a cumulative study correlating all these parameters with outcome in inferior wall STEMI patients is relatively lacking. Keeping in view of all these facts, the purpose of this study was to assess the clinical, electrocardiographic, echocardiographic and coronary angiographic profile in inferior wall STEMI patients and to establish its association with the outcomes observed during hospital stay and after one-month follow-up in order to provide appropriate risk stratification method with rational management strategies.

Materials and Methods

Study design and Population: This was a single-center, hospital based, prospective, observational study which included 102 patients admitted with inferior wall STEMI at a tertiary care hospital in northeastern part of India. The study was conducted from May 2023 to May 2024 after receiving prior approval from institutional ethics committee and was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. All patients gave written informed consent. The eligible participants were the one presenting to the hospital with first episode of inferior wall STEMI (diagnosed by history, ECG & enzymes) within 12 hours of symptom onset. Patients of all age group were included in the study. Patients meeting the following criteria were excluded: Unwilling to participate or give medical records for use of research purposes, non-ST elevation MI/ unstable angina, patients with associated anterior wall MI, proved by ST elevation in anterior leads in ECG and wall motion abnormalities by echocardiography or presented with any severe comorbidities, technically inadequate echocardiography, not willing or having relative contraindications for invasive coronary angiography, undetermined culprit vessel on invasive coronary angiography, patients lost to follow-up over one-month.

Study Methodology: Clinical examination of all the patients were performed and data was collected in predesigned structured proforma after which eligible patients were assessed for electrocardiography, echocardiography and invasive coronary angiography. All the patients received standard

pharmacological treatment for inferior wall STEMI in accordance with the currently accepted guidelines. Patients eligible for reperfusion and without contraindications to fibrinolysis were treated with tenecteplase as per weight-based dosing regimen. Coronary angiography was performed within 3-24 hours after receiving fibrinolytic therapy and angioplasty with drug eluting stent was done for significant obstructive lesions. Hypertension and diabetes were defined if patients were on an anti-hypertensive or anti-diabetic drugs and/ or insulin.

Electrocardiography (ECG): ECGs of the patients were recorded using standard 12-lead and right precordial leads along with posterior leads ECGs as baseline data followed by every 6 hours for initial 2 days and then once a day until discharged. Based on the elevation observed in the ST-segment (mm) on ECG, the patients were divided into 3 categories i.e., isolated inferior wall MI, inferior wall MI with right ventricular involvement (group RVMI) and inferior wall MI with lateral wall MI. Other than ST segment elevation, based on ECG the patients were also evaluated for the presence of sinus tachycardia, high grade/complete AV block, atrial fibrillation, ventricular tachycardia/fibrillation, or bundle branch block.

2-D and Doppler Echocardiography: Assessment of LV, left atrial, aorta and septal dimensions, LV ejection fraction (by modified Simpson's method), RV fractional area change, tricuspid annular plane systolic excursion (TAPSE), right ventricular myocardial performance index (MPI), and tricuspid annular peak systolic velocity (s'), presence of severe mitral regurgitation and ventricular septal rupture evaluation were done using PHILIPS AFFINITY 70 echo machine within 48 hours of admission.

Coronary Angiography: The angiographic view using a transradial or transfemoral approach was assessed at the end of diastole in which lesion appeared most severe and computerized quantitative coronary analytical system was used to quantify the degree of stenosis and patients with >70% stenosis were defined as having obstructive CAD and were further classified having single-vessel disease (SVD) or multi-vessel disease (MVD). The patients were referred for surgery if diagnosed with MVD or severe mitral regurgitation.

Outcomes during hospitalisation based on the prognostic implications of various clinical, ECG, echocardiographic and angiographic profile were investigated for events like heart failure (acute pulmonary edema), cardiogenic shock, haemodynamically significant/sustained ventricular tachycardia/fibrillation, need for temporary pacing/permanent pacemaker implantation, longer

hospital stay (>7 days) and all-cause mortality.

Acute pulmonary edema/ heart failure was defined as pulmonary congestion observed in the chest X-ray with more than 50% of oxygen requirement or a requirement of mechanical or positive airway pressure ventilation. Persistent systolic blood pressure <90 mmHg along with abnormal peripheral perfusion or decrement in the baseline systemic blood pressure by 30 mmHg which lasted at least 30 minutes without administration of pressor agents and systolic blood pressure >90 mmHg but <110 mmHg when on external pressor agents was defined as cardiogenic shock. The patients were advised for temporary pacemaker implantation if AV block persisted despite of receiving pharmacological therapy while permanent pacemaker was implanted in patients with refractory AV block after 2 weeks during hospital stay.

Follow-up: The eligible patients were followed up over a period of one-month and reviewed for their clinical status during outdoor hospital visits and through telephonic conversation. During follow-up,

they were assessed for post MI angina, reinfarction, readmission due to heart failure and all-cause mortality.

Statistical Analysis: All data were analysed using SPSS software version 22.0 (IBM, NY, USA). Results were presented as mean value \pm standard deviation for normally distributed continuous numerical variables, and absolute number with percentages for categorical variables. Pearson Chi-square, Mann-Whitney U test and Wilcoxon W test were used to identify possible factors affecting in-hospital and one-month follow-up outcomes. All variables with a p-value of <0.05 from univariate analysis were subjected to multivariate logistic regression analysis to determine the independent predictors of outcome parameters. A p-value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

This study enrolled 102 patients with inferior wall STEMI after meeting inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Table 1: Baseline demographic details

Variables	Patients(n=102)
Age (Mean \pm SD, years)	57.98 \pm 9.02
Male, n (%)	82(80.4)
Body Mass Index (Mean \pm SD, kg/m ²)	24.36 \pm 1.91
LVEF (Mean \pm SD,%)	51.92 \pm 5
Types of MI	
Isolated Inferior wall MI, n (%)	50(49.02)
Inferior wall MI associated with RVMI, n (%)	34(33.33)
Inferolateral wall MI, n(%)	18(17.65)
Risk factors	
Hypertension, n(%)	18 (17.6)
Diabetes Mellitus, n(%)	45(44.1)
Smoking history, n (%)	38(37.3)
Dyslipidemia, n(%)	43(42.2)

LVEF: Left ventricular ejection fraction; MI: myocardial infarction; RVMI: Right ventricular myocardial infarction.

Table 1 illustrates baseline characteristics of the enrolled patients. The mean age was found to be 57.98 \pm 9.02 years and the mean BMI for the study population was 24.36 \pm 1.91kg/m². Most of the patients in the study were male (80.4%). The admitted patients possessed risk factors like diabetes mellitus (44.1%), dyslipidemia (42.2%) and hypertension (17.6%). Among 102 patients, 38 (37.3%)

patients had history of smoking. Also, classification based on symptoms like chest pain, shortness of breath, palpitation, syncope/presyncope, sweating, nausea/vomiting along with the duration of symptoms was made for the patients. The enrolled patients were also categorized into four groups based on Killip classification for MI. The mean LVEF of the study population was 51.92 \pm 5%.

Table 2: In-hospital and one-month follow-up outcomes

Outcomes	n (%)
In-hospital	
Heart failure (acute pulmonary edema)	6 (5.88)
Cardiogenic shock	13 (12.75)
Hemodynamically significant ventricular tachycardia/ventricular fibrillation	10 (9.8)
Length of hospital stay >7 days	11(10.78)
Requirement of temporary pacemaker	19 (18.63)

Requirement of permanent pacemaker	2 (1.96)
In-hospital mortality	10 (9.8)
At one-month follow-up	
Post MI angina	14 (15.22)
Heart failure re-admission	5 (5.43)
Reinfarction	2 (2.17)
Mortality at one-month followup	2 (2.17)

Data are reported as n (%).

Table 2 comprises outcomes observed in the study population during their hospital stay and at one-month follow up, which revealed that 18.63% of study population required implantation of temporary pacemaker during their hospital stay while 1.96% were implanted with permanent pacemaker. Around 12.75% of patients developed cardiogenic shock, whereas 9.8% of admitted patients had he-

modynamically significant ventricular tachycardia/ventricular fibrillation and the least developed outcome was heart failure which accounted to be 5.88% in total. Observation in outcomes after a month of follow-up exhibited 15.22% of patients with post MI angina, 5.43% with heart-failure re-admission and minor number (2.17 %) of patients developed reinfarction and mortality.

Table3: Correlation of type of MI with outcomes

Outcomes	n (%)	TYPE OF MI			p value
		Isolated Inferior MI	Inferior MI with RVMI	Inferolateral MI	
In-hospital					
Heart failure	6 (5.88)	0	1	5	0.0001*
Cardiogenic shock	13 (12.75)	0	9	4	0.0007*
Hemodynamically significant sustained VT/VF	10 (9.8)	1	6	3	0.0339*
Longer hospital stay (>7 days)	11(10.78)	1	6	4	0.0172*
Temporary pacemaker requirement	19(18.63)	4	9	6	0.0216*
Permanent pacemaker requirement	2 (1.96)	0	2	0	0.13
Hospital mortality	10 (9.8)	1	5	4	0.0263*
At one-month follow-up					
Post MI angina	14 (15.22)	2	8	4	0.0065*
Heart failure readmission	5 (5.43)	1	0	4	0.0002*
Reinfarction	2 (2.17)	0	0	2	0.0034*
Mortality at one- month follow up	2 (2.17)	1	0	1	0.3208

Data are reported as n (%). p<0.05 was considered statistically significant. MI: Myocardial infarction; RVMI: Right ventricular myocardial infarction; VT: Ventricular tachycardia; VF: Ventricular fibrillation.

Table 3 depicts the association between the type of MI i.e., isolated inferior MI, inferior MI with RVMI and inferolateral MI and outcomes in the study population. Majority of the patients had inferior MI with RVMI. The maximum observed in-hospital outcome was requirement of temporary pacemaker(18.63%) exhibiting a positive association with the type of MI (p=0.021), followed by cardiogenic shock where 9 patients out of 13 were having inferior MI with RVMI encapsulating statistically significant correlation (p<0.001), while 5 of 6 patients with inferolateral MI developed heart failure and exhibited a significant association

(p<0.001). Four different outcomes after one-month follow-up were investigated for the study population where various types of inferior wall STEMI played a major role in development of post MI angina, heart failure and reinfarction (p=0.006, <0.001,0.003, respectively). In the study population, the extent of CAD i.e., SVD and MVD had a positive association with mortality and development of post MI angina. Lower rate of mortality was observed in patients with SVD than MVD (1 vs 9; p=0.013); similarly, lower rate of post MI angina was observed in patients with SVD than MVD (2 vs 12, p=0.02) (**Table 4**).

Table 4: Association of extent of CAD with the outcomes

Outcomes	EXTENT OF CAD		
	SVD	MVD	p value
n (%)	48(47.06)	54(52.94)	
In-hospital			
Heart failure	1(2)	5(9)	0.1242

Cardiogenic shock	6(13)	7(13)	0.9942
Hemodynamically significant sustained VT/VF	3(6)	7(13)	0.2551
Longer hospital stay(>7days)	5(10)	6(11)	0.9101
Temporary pacemaker requirement	12(25)	7(13)	0.1191
Permanent pacemaker requirement	2(4)	0(0)	0.1298
Hospital mortality	1(2)	9(17)	0.01343*
At one-month follow-up			
Post MI angina	2(4)	12(22)	0.002775*
Heart failure readmission	1(2)	4(7)	0.1527
Reinfarction	0(0)	2(4)	0.1439
Mortality at one-month follow-up	0	2(4)	0.1439

Data are represented as n (%). $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. CAD: Coronary artery disease; MI: Myocardial infarction; MVD: Multi vessel disease; RVMI: Right ventricular myocardial infarction; SVD: Single vessel disease; VT: Ventricular tachycardia; VF: Ventricular fibrillation.

Discussion

This study included 102 patients with inferior wall STEMI, with an aim to establish an association between the clinical, electrocardiographic, echocardiographic, and coronary angiography parameters with the outcomes during hospital stay and at one-month follow-up in patients with inferior wall STEMI and was conducted at tertiary care hospital in India over a period of 12 months. In this observational study a wide range of variables were studied and were compared against clinical outcomes, hence the variables which claimed significant association are elaborated in the discussion.

Correlation of Clinical Profile with Outcomes:

Isolated inferior wall MI and inferior wall STEMI associated with RVMI comprised approximately one half (49.02%) and one third (33.33%) of the study population, respectively. The inferior wall STEMI associated with RVMI outlined a positive association with development of cardiogenic shock (9 out of 13, $p=0.001$), hemodynamically significant sustained VT/VF (6 of 10, $p=0.034$) and hospital stay > 7 days (6 of 11, $p=0.017$). Also, majority i.e., 9 out of 19 patients with inferior wall STEMI associated with RVMI required implantation of temporary pacemaker during their hospital stay ($p=0.022$). Higher mortality rate was observed in patients with RVMI during hospital stay (5 out of 10) and was observed to be significantly correlated ($p=0.026$). Meta-analysis conducted by Mehta et al. [12] provided clear evidence that patients with inferior MI having RV involvement are at increased risk of developing major complications, including death, cardiogenic shock, and ventricular arrhythmias. Similar study performed by Zehender et al [10] elaborated that 19% of patients had in-hospital mortality and there were 47% incidence of major complications like cardiogenic shock, ventricular fibrillation, and high degree AV block. During one-month follow-up period, inferolateral MI was found to be significantly related with development of heart failure readmission and reinfarction which accounted to be 22% and 11% respectively. This could be due to associated severe mitral regurgita-

tion, higher incidence of LV dysfunction and involvement of LCX artery in majority of such cases leading to larger infarct size. In present study, several variables like female gender, elderly population >70 years, patients with Killip class > II and risk factors like diabetes, dyslipidemia also portray as significant contributing factors that affect the prognosis of inferior wall STEMI.

Association of ECG variables with various outcomes: Prompt diagnosis of inferior wall STEMI is paramount for timely offered reperfusion therapy i.e., primary percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI). Due to its accessibility, it is easy and cost-effective to record an ECG in comparison to the other imaging techniques. The ECG parameters like ST-changes, ratio of ST elevation and ratio of the sum of ST depression in the precordial leads to the sum of elevation in inferior leads are generally important in prediction of culprit artery [13]. In this study ST changes in aVR and sum of ST depression in V1-V6 exhibited a significant correlation with the development of hospital outcomes like heart failure, cardiogenic shock, hemodynamically significant VT/VF, longer hospital stays and in-hospital mortality. Among the outcome parameters at the follow-up, ST depression at aVR was found to be positively correlated with the development of post MI angina, heart failure readmission and reinfarction while sum of ST depression in V1-V6 was found to be associated with outcomes like post MI angina, reinfarction and mortality. On applying multinomial logistic regression, sum of ST depression in precordial leads of more than 0.8 millivolt was found to be an independent predictor of in-hospital mortality. Previous studies suggested that ST depression in aVR, lateral wall extension had positive association with increased incidence of in-hospital outcomes and long-term mortality of patients with LCX related inferior wall STEMI [7,14]. Study conducted by Peterson et al [15] suggested that patients with no precordial ST segment depression had significantly less myocardial damage along with fewer complications including cardiogenic shock, second- and third-degree atrioven-

tricular block, congestive heart failure and ventricular tachycardia or fibrillation in contrast to those who had precordial ST segment depression. Hence ST segment depression is an important predictor of poor outcomes in inferior wall STEMI patients.

Association of echocardiographic variables with various outcomes: Echocardiography provides relevant information regarding diagnosis, hemodynamic monitoring, mechanical complications, LV remodeling and short-and long-term prognosis in patients with AMI. In this study, several variables like mean LVEF (%), mean RVFAC (%), mean TAPSE (mm), mean s' [cm/s], mean MPI-TDI, severe mitral regurgitation, ventricular septal rupture were measured to correlate with the in-hospital and one-month follow-up outcomes. In this study, low mean LVEF was found to be significantly correlated with heart failure, cardiogenic shock, in-hospital mortality, readmission due to heart failure and reinfarction. Also, variability in RVFAC, TAPSE score, MPI-TDI were observed to be significantly associated with the poor prognosis in the study population. Previously conducted studies stated that, the degree of ischemic mitral regurgitation was in direct proportion to the mortality risk and hence it can be a strong factor for poor prognosis in terms of mortality and heart failure in the early phase of MI [16,17].

Study of coronary angiography variables with various outcomes: In the analysis of current study, the incidence of inferior wall STEMI caused by RCA occlusion exceeds to that of LCX (76.47% and 23.53%, respectively). In comparison to RCA related prognosis, heart failure (during hospital stay and follow-up) and reinfarction was found to be more prevalent when the culprit artery was LCX and similar association was noted in the studies performed by Sohrabi et al. [14], Chenetal [7], Rasoul et al [6] and Aliet al. [18] Hence patients with LCX occlusion have high risk of developing complications and should be treated accordingly. In addition to the culprit artery, the number of vessel involvement had a significant association with the prognostic outcomes in the study population suggesting that those with MVD have higher mortality risk to that of SVD.

Limitations

This was a single-center, prospective study with no randomization or control design involvement, conducted at an urban health care facility with a small sample size and hence the findings cannot be generalized. Also, collateral circulation at angiography was not evaluated and certain variables like angioplasty procedure, number of stents implanted, number of vessels stented, involvement of other revascularization strategies and deaths related to non- cardiac cause were not recorded.

Conclusion

Patients with inferior wall STEMI represent a heterogeneous group with varying prognosis. ECG changes including ST segment changes in lead aVR, higher magnitude of the sum of ST depression in V1-V6, failed ST resolution after fibrinolysis, precordial ST depression in V4- V6, lateral wall extension and ST elevation in right sided precordial leads were found to be associated with a poor prognosis during the hospital stay and at one-month follow-up. The culprit lesion in left circumflex artery was associated with increased incidence of heart failure and reinfarction; further, MVD was found to have association with increased rate of mortality and post MI angina, as compared to SVD. Therefore, besides providing rational treatment regimen, equivalent importance should be given to identify the risks and outcomes using indicators such as clinical profile, electrocardiography, echocardiography, and coronary angiography parameters to take rational therapeutic decisions in the management of patients with inferior wall STEMI.

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